

The Influence Of Service Quality Perseption Toward Inpatient Satisfaction At Mayjen H.A Thalib Hospital Kerinci 2016

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ABSTRACT

Background: In the global era, that becomes indicators of success of health service is a inpatient satisfaction. Patient will fell satisfied if they gain the health service more than their hope. There are five indicators of inpatient satisfaction are *reliability, tangibles, responsiveness, assurance, emphaty*.

Method: This research was the quantitative reserch with design cross sectional that has towards to know the influence of service quality perseption with inpatient satisfaction at Mayjen H.A Thalib Hospital Kerinci. Sample technique was propotional sampling, the samples were 95 respondens. Data were tested by chi-square test.

Result: The result was the patient felt satisfied with the servis health that given from Mayjen H.A Thalib Hospital Kerinci, and there were influence between perseption of service quality dimensions of *reliability, responsiveness, assurance andemphaty* toward inpatient satisfaction with the p-value 0.000, in addition there was no influence between perseption of service quality dimension of tangible with the p-value 0.647.

Conclusion: Researcher hope that the hospital can set the schedule to medicinal treatment, with the result that the patient will not wait too long.

Keywords : *Perseption of quality service and Inpatient Satisfaction.*

BACKGROUND

Quality of health services is the degree of perfection of health services that can satisfy every user of health care services in accordance with the level of satisfaction of the average population, and who organize it in accordance with predetermined standards and

professional codes of ethics by adjusting the potential resources that are available fairly, efficiently and effective and safely provided, and satisfactory in accordance with norms, ethics, law, and socio-culture with due regard to the limitations and capabilities of government and consumer societies (Morgan, Rebecca L, 2003).

The quality of health service in the hospital needs to be measured by measuring every dimension of health service quality to know the level of patient satisfaction and reuse (Juran and Maxwell in Pohan, 2012).

In this era of globalization, the indicator of the success of health services in hospitals is patient satisfaction (Tjiptono, 2008). Patient satisfaction is a level of patient feeling that arises as a result of the health-care performance it receives after the patient compares it to what is expected (Pohan, 2006).

Patient satisfaction is very subjective, difficult to measure, changeable, and there are many factors that influence as much dimension in human life. Subjectivity can be reduced and can even be objective if enough similar opinions to something. Therefore, to examine patient satisfaction is used a research instrument that is valid enough accompanied by good research method (Suryawati C, 2004).

According to Zeithaml-Pasuraman-Berry (Pasolong, 2007), to know the quality of services perceived significantly by consumers, there are indicators of customer satisfaction that lies in the five dimensions of service quality. Those five dimensions are reliability, tangibles, responsiveness, assurance, empathy. According Suryani

(2008) approach to service quality and customer satisfaction became one of the important strategies that can not be ignored.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a quantitative research with cross sectional design which aims to know the influence of health service quality in dimension of reliability, quick response, assured, empathy and physical proof to the satisfaction of inpatient patient at Major General H.A Thalib Hospital, Kerinci Regency.

The samples in this study were 95 respondents and sampling technique proportional each room of inpatient. This study was conducted on September 22 - October 3, 2016. The data obtained were processed using chi-square test.

RESEARCH RESULT

Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1 shows that the characteristics of respondents by sex are from 95 respondents, there are 47 respondents (49.5%) with male gender and 48 respondents (50.5%) with female gender. Characteristics of respondents based on age got age of adolescents (18-25 years) as many as 5 people (5.3%), adult age (26-54 years) as many as 70 rang (73.7%), and elderly (46-50) 20 people (21.1%).

Tabell
Univariate Analysis Respondent's Respondent Characteristics Based on Sex, Age, Education and Occupation at Inpatient Room of Major General H.A Thalib Hospital, Kerinci District, 2016

Variabel	Frekuensi (n)	Persentase (%)
Sex		
Male	47	49,5
Female	48	50,5
Age		
18-25 year	5	5,3
26-45 year	70	73,7
46-50 year	20	21,1
Education		
Collage	12	
Senior High School	43	12,6
Junior High School	40	45,3
		42,1
Occupation		
Housewife	36	
Farmer	22	37,9
Civil servant	6	23,2
Empoyess	21	6,3
entrepreneur	10	22,1
		10,5

For respondent's characteristic on the basis of education, 45.3% of senior high school educated respondents, the rest are Junior High School 42.1%, and 12.6% Higher Education, and job-based

characteristics as housewife (IRT) 37 , 9%, the rest of the farmers are 23.2%, private sector is 22.1%, self-employed 10.5%, and civil servant 6.3%.

Tabel2
Distribution of Respondents' Satisfaction on Service at Inpatient Room of Major General H.A Thalib Hospital, Kerinci District, 2016.

No	Question	Perception		Expectation		Gap
		Total	Mean	Total	Mean	
1	Reliability	220	2,31	254	2,68	-0,37
2	Quick Response	274	2,9	208	2,2	0,7
3	Guaranteed quality	220	2,32	259	2,73	-0,41
4	Emphaty	270	2,85	207	2,2	0,65
5	Physical evidence	270	2,84	209	2,2	0,64
	Mean	250,8	2,6	227,4	2,4	0,2

Ket : Nilai Mean : 3 (Baik) ; 2 (Cukup Baik) ; 1 (Tidak Baik)

Nilai Gep = Tidak Puas (-2 s/d -0,7) ; Cukup Puas (>0,7 s/d 0,6) ; Puas (> 0,6 s/d

From the five dimensions of the quality of health services obtained overall value, patient satisfaction on the

quality of health services in the inpatient room Major General H.A Thalib Kerinci

Tabel 3
Effect of Quality Perception of Health Service on Patient Satisfaction at Inpatient Room of Major General H.A Thalib Hospital, Kerinci District, 2016

Quality of Service	Kepuasan Pasien								P-value
	Not satisfied		Quite satisfied		Satisfied		Total		
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Reliability									
Bad	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Passably	28	49	29	51	0	0	57	100	
Good	2	5,3	36	94,7	0	0	38	100	
Quick Response									
Bad	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Passably	0	0	6	100	0	0	6	100	
Good	0	0	21	24	68	76	89	100	
Guaranteed quality									
Bad	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Passably	33	59	23	41	0	0	56	100	
Good	0	0	38	97	1	3	39	100	

district with a value of 0.2 gap which means that patients feel quite satisfied with the quality of health services provided to them.

Quality of Service	Kepuasan Pasien								<i>P</i> -value
	Not satisfied		Quite satisfied		Satisfied		Total		
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Emphaty									
Bad	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.000
Passably	0	0	7	100	0	0	7	100	
Good	0	0	20	23	68	77	88	100	
Physical evidence									
Bad	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.647
Passably	0	0	3	60	2	40	5	100	
Good	0	0	37	41	33	59	90	100	

In table 3 above obtained *p*-value 0.000 for service quality dimensions reliability, quick response, guaranteed and empathy, if compared with the value of α 0.05 which means the value of *p*-value is smaller than the value α which means that there is a significant influence of perception respondents on the quality of health services to

patient satisfaction in the dimensions of reliability, quick response, assured and empathy. And the value of *p*-value 0.647 for the quality of service dimension of physical evidence, which means there is no significant influence between the quality of service dimensions of physical evidence of patient satisfaction in inpatient ward of Major General H.A thalib District Kerinci in 2016.

DISCUSSION

1. Dimensions of Reliability and Patient Satisfaction

The results showed that patients felt quite satisfied with the health service dimension of reliability at Major General H.A Thalib Hospital Kerinci. Hospital service schedule is fast and precise is the patient's highest expectation on the dimensions of reliability because the examination or treatment of patients is often delayed due to delayed health personnel in conducting the examination, but patients still judge that the service has been given quite well.

Patient acceptance services that must be fast and precise is also the highest expectation of patients, based on the results of patient care research conducted by health workers at Major General Hospital HA Thalib is fast and accurate, health workers always receive patients by directly checking the patient's

condition and treat patients with alacrity without must perform a convoluted procedure first, so that patients feel quite satisfied with the quality of health service dimension of reliability in the inpatient ward of Major General HA Thalib District Kerinci.

The results also indicate that there is a significant influence of the perception of health service quality on patient satisfaction, as evidenced from the value of p-value 0.000. There are 57 respondents who considered quite satisfied with the service, but 28 of them feel not satisfied, as well as 38 respondent who rate the service good 2 of them also feel not satisfied. This is due to the lack of patient knowledge of hospital procedures to be followed, so according to some of them the procedures made by the hospital are too complicated, as well as the delay in doctors' scheduling of patients who are often less timely, but based on the overall observation of the service patient in terms of schedule examination, acceptance and treatment of patients already follow hospital procedures that have been determined and already meet the expectations of patients.

Tjong (2004) argues that reliability or reliability of services will be provided if credible by the customer includes service should be consistent, and Melanie et al (2013) argue that convoluted service and length of waiting period can determine the quality of health service because it makes the patient feel not well served so that this can lead to dissatisfaction.

Mukhti, MY, et al (2013) states that the dimension of timeliness, explaining that in order to succeed, the health services must be carried out in the right time and manner, by appropriate service providers, and using appropriate tools and drugs, as well as cost-efficient. Timeliness in service is the ability of hospitals to provide services in accordance with the promised, which includes the speed and accuracy of officers in providing services include: accuracy in the procedure of patient acceptance, enrollment, waiting time, time examined and diagnose disease and cure of disease.

This research is in line with the research of Hermanto, D (2010) which examined about the effect of midwifery service perception on the satisfaction of the inpatients of midwifery in Dr. H. Soemarno Sosroatmodjo Bulungan East Kalimantan which states that, there is influence perception of quality of obstetric care service with patient satisfaction with p-value value 0.001.

2. Quick Dimension of Response and Patient Satisfaction

Rapid response in this study is the patient's response regarding the speed and accuracy of the officer in dealing with patient complaints and responsive in meeting the needs of patients. Based on the gap value between the dimensions of tangap quickly with patient satisfaction known that the patient was satisfied with the services provided, because the services provided to patients is greater than the expectations of patients.

Based on the results of research, there is a significant influence between the perception of the quality of service dimension quickly responsive to patient satisfaction with p-value 0.000. Patients assess that the services provided in the form of information and treatment of patient complaints is quite good. In giving information to patients, the officer explained in detail and clearly to the family or patient about the disease and everything related to the treatment given to the patient, and also the health officer at Major General HA Thalib Hospital Kerinci always fast and swift in handling any complaints patient.

James (2013) states that responsiveness and sensitivity to patient needs will improve the quality of care in nursing care. Wijono (2011) also argues from the point of view of service users, the quality of health services is the service which can fulfill all keingginan or patient needs in a respectful, respectful, responsive, and friendly manner. The result is similar to Asmuji's (2013) opinion that perception of responsiveness with patient satisfaction is the result of stimulus and the patient's senses from received services will be perceived so that later will be able to assess the quality of service, if what they expect in accordance with the reality they get, it will be able to provide satisfaction to the patient to the nurse's responsiveness, and vice versa if what they expect does not match the reality then the patient is not satisfied.

3. Dimensions of Patient Guarantee and Satisfaction

Assured dimensions are the patient's response to quality assurance of service in terms of worker's skills in work and polite and friendly service. Based on the gap value between guaranteed dimensions and patient satisfaction is known that the patient is quite satisfied with the services provided, and there is an influence between the perception of quality service dimension assured to patient satisfaction.

The service officers provided by Major General HA Thalib Hospital are health workers who have sufficient experience and knowledge in conducting disease diagnosis and diagnosis, and also every health worker is required to greet every patient with smile and courtesy and to provide security in service to every patient.

According to Wathek (2012) Guarantees on the quality of services related to the knowledge of employees and their ability in growing trust and confidence of customers to health services.

4. Empathy and Patient Satisfaction

The empathy dimension is the patient's response to the attention given by the officer to the patient and the patient's family. Both in providing medical and non medical services. Based on the gap value between the empathy dimension with patient satisfaction known that the patient was satisfied with the services provided, and there is influence between the perception of quality service empathy dimension to patient satisfaction.

The services provided by health workers at Major General H.A Thalib

Hospital do not regard social status or nursing class for each patient, and always listen to patient complaints. Attitude and quick response of health workers to patients who provide a sense of satisfaction with the services provided. Health workers always provide solutions and solutions for each complaining patient, and also always prioritize harmonious relationships between patients and health workers.

Dimension Empathy (empathy) means, giving a genuine concern to patients who are individual or personal who seeks in understanding the wishes of patients (Asmuji, 2013). According Jacobalis (in Asmuji, 2013) patient dissatisfaction is often raised against the attitude and behavior of hospital personnel and officers less communicative and informative with patients.

5. Physical Evidence and Patient Satisfaction

The dimension of physical evidence in this study is the patient's response to the physical appearance of the officers and hospital buildings. Based on the gap value between the physical evidence dimension and patient satisfaction it is known that the patient is satisfied with the service provided, and there is no significant influence between the perception of the quality of the health service dimension of physical proof to patient satisfaction.

Spatial exterior and interior Hospital Major General H.A Thalib Kerinci district in the design with such a way and follow the requirements of the

appropriate hospital layout in order to create a sense of comfort and safety to each patient. Cleanliness of the hospital is also always maintained, with every morning and afternoon there is always a janitor who will clean every room of the hospital. The health worker also always maintains hygiene and self-sanitation, using clean clothes and always replaced and always wash his hands with alcohol every time after and before checking the patient, in order to keep the infected germs from himself or from his own patients. Completeness and cleanliness of every tool used is also always maintained, with mensterilisasikan first every tool that will be used before checking the patient.

Parasuraman et al (1988) in Muninjaya (2011), the quality of health services can also be felt directly by its users by providing adequate physical facilities and equipment. These include: the appearance of physical facilities such as buildings and front office space, the availability of parking space, cleanliness, tidiness and comfort of the room, the appearance of officers, the completeness of equipment and communication services.

CONCLUSION

From the results of the research based on the gap value obtained, that for dimensions of reliability and quality assured patient satisfied, and for the dimension of quick response, empathy and physical evidence of patients are satisfied with the quality of services provided in the inpatient room Major General Hospital HA Thalib Kerinci District in 2016.

The result of the research shows that there is a significant influence between the quality of health service dimension of reliability, quick response, assured, and empathy with patient satisfaction in patient ward of Major General H.A Thalib Hospital Kerinci in 2016 with p-value 0.000.

There is no significant influence between the quality of health service dimension of physical proof with patient satisfaction in patient ward of Major General H.A Thalib Hospital, Kerinci regency in 2016 with p-value 0.647.

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